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Editors

Jazmín Mota
Adrián Fernández

Editorial design

Héctor Ortega

Writing/Collaboration

Rafael Muñiz
Natalia Millán
Marilú Rojas
Lorena Morales
Violeta E. Cardona

Cover:

Stijn Dijkstra - Pexel

MeCCS

The Mexican Carbon Capture
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<https://meccs.org.mx/>

✉ puntocritico@meccs.org.mx

🌐 [linkedin.com/company/meccs](https://www.linkedin.com/company/meccs)

📷 @MeCCS.plataforma

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Editor's note

In this newsletter edition, we explore how spirituality can guide our actions towards a more sustainable life. Various links between spirituality and sustainability start from a perspective of connection with nature that goes beyond immediacy and the material, which invites us to contemplate the world with greater awareness and reverence to act in accordance with the fact that our existence is intrinsically linked to the planet's future.

In this issue, we present three notes on spirituality and sustainability, in which MeCCS members, Rafael Muñiz López, animator of the Laudato Si' Movement Mexico, and Natalia Millán, researcher at the Complutense University of Madrid. Also, we had the opportunity to interview Marilú Rojas, a feminist theologian and professor at the Universidad Iberoamericana and Universidad La Salle, who has addressed spirituality's central position in the face of socio-environmental problems. In the *Yes, yes it is* section, we added two infographics: the first about one of the *good lives* that emanate from the Masewal culture, and the second by Violeta Cardona, from the UNAM's Postgraduate program in Sustainability, about the healing the body-territory as a cosmogonic and political path. To complement the topic addressed in this edition, we share some recommendations for books, magazines, interviews and audiovisual material linked to the points that connect sustainability and spirituality.

ABOUT INTERCONNECTIONS AND EPIGRAPHS

By **Adrián Fernández
y Jazmín Mota,
MeCCS**

*For those who look without seeing,
the earth is just earth.
The pampa, nor the stream,
nor the willow bush tells them nothing.*

Atahualpa Yupanqui

Literary epigraphs are quotes that appear at the beginning of a text and have varied functions: they can introduce key ideas; sometimes, they are trailers or spoilers for the work. Sometimes, they serve as tributes; sometimes, they show the sources that inspired the work. Technically, these short quotes are part of the paratext: a kind of threshold or boundary between what is inside and outside the text. In this paratextual environment, of course, there are exchanges as if they were border zones.

One of these exchanges is clear in *Silent Spring*, by the biologist and activist Rachel Carson, published in 1962. The epigraph of this work is a dedication to Albert Schweitzer, which Carson took from a fragment of a letter that the German polymath wrote to a beekeeper whose bees had died due to the presence of pesticides:

*Man has lost the capacity to foresee and to forestall.
He will end by destroying the Earth.*

After that epigraph that gave framework to the work, Carson denounced the effects of the indiscriminate use of pesticides on human health and ecological balance. His work had a profound impact on environmental movements and the creation of organizations, such as the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), dedicated to protecting the environment.

The aforementioned Albert Schweitzer, in 1915, during a boat trip on the Ogowé River in Gabon, observed a herd of migrant hippos at the same time that the idea of reverence for life materialized in him – suddenly. Years later, he wrote that the concept is a philosophical position that supports life as intrinsically valuable. In his vision, the basic experience of a human being is an affinity with his surroundings and awareness of the interconnection between all living and non-living beings. Schweitzer's image oscillates between criticism for being a well-intentioned but paternalistic European and, on the other hand, the perception of an extremely virtuous person due to his tireless work in West Africa to combat malaria, leprosy and whooping cough. This humanitarian work, the development of a philosophical position, and the possibility of establishing a universal ethics based precisely on the idea of reverence for life earned him the Nobel Peace Prize (1953).

Of course, in many spaces and at many times, the idea of reverence for life has been expressed. Whether through trance, meditation, reflection, prayer, deep joy, or even everyday life, sacred experiences and visions can be had. Whatever the medium, one of the outcomes is that other worlds are revealed; they show themselves interconnected, and we are with them. When Canadian anthropologist Jeremy Narby entered the Amazon with Indigenous communities to learn about the alliance and forms of communication between shamans and nature, he concluded that there is a form of intelligence in nature that refers to the fact that all living beings have what in Japanese can be conceptualized as *chi-sei*: the ability to know.

Narby argues that there is a problem with concepts and definitions that clearly denotes the divergence between Western and Indigenous knowledge. The first is based on a mechanistic principle; the second is based on a "system of knowledge" that leads to the recognition that all living beings have a spirit or a force that makes them venerable. Although the intelligence of nature until now continues to be put on the margins, to know it, according to Narby, it is enough to go out into the world and observe it and marvel at this "great mystery." An idea that he himself places as an epigraph in his work *Intelligence in Nature*, through a quote attributed to Heraclitus, the master of paradoxes, since hiding and discovering are variations of the same and one cannot exist without the other:

Nature loves to hide.¹

Another clear manifestation of reverence for life is in Jainism, which is strongly based on the concept of *jiva* – the soul, the vital force, the immortal essence – and on the principle of *ahimsa* (non-violence) of thought, word and action. A fundamental point is that this principle must be practiced towards ourselves and all living beings since we all have *jiva*. This idea is not only in the religious context but also in politics. For example, in the concept of the body-territory, born of the ecofeminist movement, it is argued that the human body is in itself a territory, an extension of the natural environment where all kinds of conflicts, exploitation and abuses occur and are expressed that must be challenged. to end all forms of violence. In the book *Mirrors of Him*, the Uruguayan journalist and writer Eduardo Galeano presents as an epigraph an Indigenous song from South Dakota that expresses the sacred between the body and the land:

Father, paint the world on my body.

Non-violence, the sacredness of nature and reverence for life are condensed, for example, in the iconic *Chipko Movement*. In the mountainous region of Uttarakhand, India, some Chamoli residents, especially women, used non-violent methods to protect their forests from commercial logging activities. His act of hugging trees was and is a powerful symbol of environmental activism. Likewise, the Andean Action initiative in Peru, Chile, Bolivia, Argentina and Ecuador has managed to save and restore more than 36 thousand hectares of high Andean forests where communities – and again, many women – put *Chakana*, a symbol and worldview, into practice, of the Andean culture that remembers the cultural heritage and ancestral wisdom that connects multiple generations in time and space with all things and beings on this planet.

We can also highlight the actions of Wangari Maathai, an African biologist who won the Nobel Peace Prize (2004) and who tirelessly opted for non-violent acts that could shake and even dismantle structures of oppression in her native Kenya. Her Green Belt movement began as an effort to ensure that women in rural communities could meet their basic needs. In the last 50 years, this movement has seen 50 million trees grow. The notion of environmental respect of *Mama Titi* (Mother of the Trees), as some people call her, is based on the teachings that her grandmother instilled in her when she was a child, explaining that a large fig tree near her house was sacred. and, therefore, was not to be disturbed.

Back to the epigraphs, Wangari Maathai, in his work *Replenishing the Earth*, refers to a comment by a Jewish rabbi (Qohelet Rabbah) to Ecclesiastes (7:13):

Here are my works. See how beautiful they are, how excellent! Everything I have created, I did for your good. Make sure you don't ruin and destroy my world because if you do, there will be no one to repair it after you.

¹ One of several forms that have been used for the translation of the Greek physis kryptesthai philei.

We can find this sense of gratitude, respect and reverence for life in many cultures worldwide that, although geographically distant, are close in their worldviews and values. In Mexico, the concept of Yeknemelis (*yek* = pure, good, true, and *nemelis* = life), or good living, of the Masewal culture invites us to honor the nature of which we are part, the work of the ancestors and to ensure the well-being of future generations. All these ideas shared by various communities, without a doubt, are pillars of sustainability.

John E. Carroll, an American professor of environmental conservation, explains that charting paths toward sustainability involves questioning our values as a society that are highly rooted in efficiency, technology or economics and instead turning toward an experience of conversion to develop a deep spirituality. It should be noted that deep spirituality is not exclusive to a few "elevated" people but is something intrinsic and naturally accessible to each person, each being and territory. Although some sociocultural practices and experiences may seem to prevent the spirit from being and coexisting with other spirits, everything is interconnected.

The spirit is that which animates us, gives us life, and chooses transcendence, admiration, and reverence for something greater, for the complete image... In a certain way, spirituality and sustainability converge since both are based on determination and the goal of prevailing. Then, the term "sustainability", in its most used meaning, becomes superficial and trivialized since true sustainability requires big changes in value systems. The task of changing predominant thinking and behavior is titanic, but many of these changes are immersed in our daily actions: in thoughts of gratitude for the nature of which we are part; in the dissolution of the self by choice of the community; in the opening of feelings and reasoning to recognize the sacredness of the environment; and in the multiple ways of revering life.

Being spiritual and moving towards sustainability is an achievable state. Surely, all of us, at some point, have had an episode similar to that of Schweitzer on the Ogowe River. We have perceived ourselves as a piece – albeit small – of an interconnected being-space-time. Thích Nhất Hạnh, a Buddhist monk, activist and poet, called *interbeing* the representation of the interdependence of existence. In those moments, we have, well, *interbe*. True change can only occur through a deeper state of interconnectedness, which is the sustainability we seek.

Being one with our siblings and sister Mother Earth: Franciscan spirituality

By **Fr. Rafael Muñiz López**. Archdiocese of Xalapa, Ver., Mexico.
Animator of the Laudato Si' Movement Mexico.

Every day, human beings seek to be immortalized. That phrase I heard for the first time as a teenager comes to mind: *"if you want to be remembered, write a book, plant a tree and have a child"*, all with the desire to leave a mark for subsequent generations to talk about you. However, it is not easy for people to transcend their time, their faith and their legacy.

Giovanni di Pietro Bernardone, later known as Saint Francis of Assisi, was born in 1182 in a small town in present-day Italy. Although he died eight centuries ago, he is one of those people who, without seeking to be immortalized, has remained a light for many of his disciples thanks to his way of life, being and manifesting his relationship with the environment and nature. His life and work inspired and motivated important movements and changes in the society of his time and have transcended to the present day.

Like every young man of his time, Francisco dreamed of being a knight and defending his city and guild since his father was a cloth merchant. He sought to be recognized for his nobility and feats in battle, a feeling that was part of his human condition. However, this apprentice knight ended up in prison, suffering from hunger, cold, ridicule, and disease, and despite this, his great desire for human glory persisted. Then, he first encountered someone not so well known to him, God, who in a dream asked him: *"Who do you want to serve: the master or the laborer?"* This event would change the course of his life.

Undoubtedly, one of the decisive events in his life was the encounter with a leper on the plain of Assisi, someone who was usually rejected and who, instead, awakened in him a deep sense of love. From then on, his relationships would be more human, deeper and more fraternal since he would perceive himself as part of a great family where all created beings share a brotherhood, being children of the same father. Thus, he began a process that changed his way of contemplating and relating to his surroundings. This experience marked a change in Francis' mentality and way of living: he detached himself from his material goods and embarked on a new path or spirituality that was like a light that illuminated society and the Church in the following centuries.

In the autumn of 1205, his life was turned upside down by a mystical encounter in the almost-collapsed church of San Damiano. As Thomas of Celano (1247) transmits it: *“Already perfectly changed in his heart, about to also change in his body, he walks one day near the church of San Damiano [...] he prostrates himself supplicating and devout before the crucifix, and [...] in this trance, the image of Christ speaks from the painting to Francis and says ‘go, repair my house, which, as you see, is completely falling to the ground’* (Franciscan biographical sources [IDEAM]. s.f).¹ This and other events led him to discover a divine experience that transformed his life.

Saint Francis is a key figure when it comes to brotherhood and harmonious relationships with his environment, starting with the inclusion and acceptance of those usually rejected by society. His way of being began to have a deep impact on the society of his time, which had well-marked social strata. Despite this, his proposal for equality and the abandonment of desires for accumulation would be two of the characteristic signs of his work.

For him, poverty was the path to total freedom and to be a light for the church, which he had to restore and for the people. If nothing tied him to this world, then freedom allowed him to move quickly without accumulating anything. His path to spirituality gave birth to a new order¹ that would reach unimaginable dimensions, sustained by charity and kindness towards other people and the environment, transcending geographical borders. However, as he belonged to the Catholic community, he required the approval of his superiors, so he presented himself before Pope Innocent III, who recognized the new order. This can also be seen as a revolutionary act since it represents a sign of poverty for a Church where other types of interests existed.

Perhaps Saint Francis never appreciated the scope of his actions. Still, he turned a process of contemplation into an act that transformed social structures and raised new relationships between people, the environment and nature. One of his most revolutionary works is, without a doubt, *The Canticle of the Creatures*, a text written in romance and considered the first Italian poem. This prayer is, above all, a praise to God, where creation is named in an intrinsic brotherhood: the Sun, the Moon, the stars, the wind, water, fire and earth. It is the universe itself praising the Lord. In this song, Saint Francis transmits a message of communion with all the brother elements, all created by God himself and for which we must be co-responsible and with whom we must coexist in harmony.

The *Canticle of the Creatures* and the values of Francis of Assisi can be clearly reflected in one of the fundamental documents in the field of sustainability: the encyclical *Laudato Si'*, published by Pope Francis in 2015, which highlights the urgent need for global ecological conversion. Hand in hand with Franciscan teachings, sustainability in the encyclical is shown to be inseparable from social and economic justice. *Laudato Si'* has become a perennial and universal invitation that calls for collective action to protect the common home by focusing on critical issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution, but also by reviewing criticism of the development and consumption models that dominate our society.

This encyclical, considered by some to be one of the most inspiring integral ecology documents in these times of global crisis, is the inspiration for the creation of a global movement of the same name. The *Laudato Si' Movement* works to achieve social and ecological justice through the Catholic community and in coordination with people of other faiths, diverse cultures and beliefs based on spiritual transformation, common care, building bridges for collaboration and, above all, embracing contemplation and action.

Coming to this moment in the 21st century, it is still essential to strive to be more contemplative to recognize and connect with the beauty and sacredness of our environment as Saint Francis did at the time, but, at the same time, we must recognize the shortcomings that people experience. the smallest, the poor, the marginalized, the voiceless. Of course, we need to listen to our common home, the planet, which is the place where we live and which we must respect and care for like the rest of the divine creations with which we share our existence.

Learn more about the Laudato Si' Movement at <https://laudatosimovement.org>

¹ A religious order is an association of people who have come together to follow a tradition focused on prayer, contemplation, teaching, social work, or helping those in need.

Politics, emotions and spirituality

By Natalia Millán, Universidad Complutense de Madrid

In this fragmented and one-dimensional world where we have been taught that there is only one desirable model of living and being, the predominant idea is that each space of human experience must be divided, separated into small unconnected parts that break down the facets of life.

Based on the way in which our societies have been built, politics is part of the public space and is conceived as a game of power, partisan and interested, distanced from any vision of the common good. Emotions, for their part, belong to the personal sphere and are often understood as secondary and inferior spheres of human identity. Spiritual perspectives are then visions that are almost forbidden since transcendental questions are inappropriate and undesirable elements for those of us who play the role of effective, productive and competent subjects in an increasingly commercialized and demanding system.

The power devices have created a system organized through material policies, institutions, and actors that configures ideas, values and beliefs about what an individual should be: an eminently rational, analytical and efficient being that adapts perfectly to the supply

and demand dynamics. This is how the idea of the human being has been constructed as a mental subject that, in this framework, denies and makes invisible the rest of the dimensions of the being: the corporal, the social, the emotional and the spiritual.

The denial of the multidimensionality of being in the contemporary public sphere (Source: own elaboration).

Repressing these dimensions of the being generates a fragmentation and a vital uprooting in human beings that triggers impossibilities and limits to the development of our consciousness, critical sense, and freedom. Without the tools and abilities to know what we are and what we need, we will hardly be able to have

a full and free life. It is on these impossibilities that, in my opinion, the entire system of power is structured. In this sense, the intimate and personal, which is the construction of the identity of the being, is also deeply political. Therefore, there is an unfathomable implication between politics, emotions and spirituality.

The denial of the multidimensionality of being as a cardinal axis of constructing an unequal, violent and commercialized system (Source: own elaboration).

I think we are in a very complex and critical moment for humanity. The capitalist, patriarchal and colonial system of production and consumption is leading us not only to an unprecedented ecological crisis but also to an increasingly violent and unequal system where the most basic elements of human rights and the peaceful organization of people are questioned. life together. At this time of crisis of democracy, genocides, ecocides and the emergence of authoritarian and reactionary options in the West, it is difficult to imagine horizons of hope and harmony in the construction of a more just and sustainable world.

When analyzing these dynamics, a feeling of hopelessness and disconsolation permeates. However, I would like to share a small political message of hope. Despite the violence and denial of the other in our political scenarios, I observe a profound spiritual awakening in an important part of humanity. So, there is hope.

I think it is possible to affirm that never before in history have there been so many people carrying out public work deeply intertwined with integral, emotional and spiritual growth. More and more people are engaging in practices and studies focused on compassion, meditation and personal healing in search of personal transformation that transcends the world in which we live. I see more and more communities focused on respectful parenting, connection with nature, integrative healing processes, and the study of spiritualities and religions, as well as open to dialogue and common construction to imagine a more loving and peaceful world with all the beings that live in it. We inhabit this planet.

I believe, or at least that is my desire, that it is time to bring this awakening to the field of politics and social organization, because the very essence of the concept of politics is precisely the harmonious and equitable management of life in common. Politics arises from the awareness that we are fragile beings and need others to live, grow and be happy. Therefore, politics can promote the noble path of creating spaces where all beings can live and develop free of violence and fear. True politics must guide the construction of the common good, just as true spirituality must be based on compassion, community ethics and dedication to others.

We can develop an integrative proposal that stops fragmenting human beings and creates a more just and kind world for us, our children and all the beings that inhabit this planet.

Learn more about Natalia's work:
<http://ucm.academia.edu/NataliaMill%C3%A1n>

CONVERSING

THE ACTIVE SENSE OF SPIRITUALITY

Interview with **Marilú Rojas**, Universidad Iberoamericana
by **Jazmín Mota y Lorena Morales**

Talking about spirituality seems like an almost abstract topic restricted to the mystical and the unknown that escapes human reasoning. However, at some point in our lives, we have all had an experience that connects us with the divine and the transcendental. When this happens, it is difficult to deny the existence of something that gives us life and allows us to feel and connect with ourselves and the nature of which we are a part. Perhaps we think of spirituality as a static and contemplative thing exclusive to religious environments and practices, but what if it were something within the reach of anyone? What if we took it to the field of action? Living, walking, dancing, fighting, and loving are how we connect and transform.

In this interview, we talk with Marilú Rojas about spiritualities and the meaning they gain when we address the great socio-environmental challenges from a more plural, critical and active perspective.

Marilú was born in Orizaba, Veracruz, Mexico. She holds a doctorate in Systemic Theology from the Catholic University of Leuven, Belgium. Her doctoral thesis was on ecofeminist spiritualities and theologies in Latin America. She is a feminist theologian and professor at the Universidad Iberoamericana and Universidad La Salle. She is a founding member of TEIFEM (Feminist Theologians and Researchers of Mexico) and director of the magazine *Sophias* (a journal of interdisciplinary reflection on feminist theology in Mexico). In addition, she is part of the founding group of the Academy of Theology in Mexico of the Pontifical University. She is a member of the DARE (Discernment and Radical Engagement), which is part of the Council for World Mission. She is dedicated to feminist practice and, from there, connects with the community spiritualities of indigenous women. She is Catholic and academic, demonstrating the coexistence of these two positions with the conviction that spirituality is the force that positions us before life and politically for the common good of all the beings that inhabit this planet that we call Earth.

J: Marilú, could you tell us what spiritualities are?

M: The word spirituality comes from the Latin *spiritus*, which was related to the subjective, the non-real, and the transcendental. The word's origin is connected with *Ruâh*, in Hebrew, which means **vital breath**. And from there, I return to the concept of a vital breath. So, what is spirituality? Our way of living, the force that inhabits us, this inner force that made us get up this morning to be here, that potentiality that inhabits every living being. From this vision, we also break with anthropocentrism and with a situation of species supremacy because we humans are not the only ones who have that strength or the ability to think, to learn, to communicate. Plants and animals have their spirit, their *ruâh*, their vital breath. In indigenous peoples, it is said that they have their *nahual* or their *totem*, which is a connection and inner strength. The Earth also has its spirituality, so do the forest, the water, the sky, and the cosmos.

Spirituality is this relational capacity that inhabits us and this dynamic force in which we establish different relationships, get to know each other and learn from each other and others. And also, in this, I connect with Rosi Braidotti, a post-humanist feminist who criticizes anthropocentrism and says that now we also need to learn to relate to a new species: artificial intelligence. So, there will also be a relationship with technology, and we will have to talk about a spirituality that goes beyond humans. There will then be post-humanist spiritualities beyond the relationships between humans and interspecies relationships, that is, with the cosmos and with technology, breaking precisely with the hierarchies where some are above other species.

Inevitably, we will have to think that human beings are not the owners of this planet, that we are not the owners of the Earth, the cosmos, and the water, and the species. So, the big ecological problem, for example, is the logic of hoarding, ownership, and hierarchization. We want to take over and use nature, but we are not interested in planting plants or trees. We are not interested in denouncing the injustice of those who monopolize resources. There is a process of devastation, and there is a process of ownership that governments have no will to resolve, and neither do we citizens.

J: There is a human-nature (or bodies-territories) relationship based on consumption and waste that is given and rarely criticized. Do you think it would be possible to redefine this relationship from spiritualities?

M: Spiritualities are a path that can help us, allowing us to create more critical awareness of what we are experiencing and where we want to go as humanity, but it is not the only option. Let us think, for instance, of the war in Gaza, which is not only a war built around colonizing the promised land but also because Gaza is a territory that has water, and Israel wants that water. Another example is Ukraine, which has many natural resources, or Chiapas, Mexico, where the great curse of our people is their natural wealth. But this is not a curse coming from divinity, but a curse coming from patriarchal neoliberal capitalism that wants to take possession of all those goods, what Rita Laura Segato calls *dueñez*¹. The idea is that I want to take over the earth body, the water body, and the air body, no matter what I must do to achieve it.

So, ecofeminisms and ecofeminist spiritualities are not romantic ideas of planting trees and eating naturally because sometimes they think of us that way, as something very romantic. No, it's not just that. It is a **political stance that denounces a predatory system** in which patriarchal states are complicit. We need to learn to live together, to relate and to make other policies, other forms of economy that are not predatory, nor colonialist, nor neoliberal, but rather an economy of the common good for everyone—an economy where the rest of the species are not affected either.

J: Usually, when we hear the word spirituality, we think of it as a very contemplative and passive thing. But what you propose is something different, a call to action, to defense, to the union, to denounce. What could you tell us about it?

M: The contemplative mode is mysticism or prayer; one can contemplate a sunset or nature. However, I am not referring to this type of spirituality but to that which has a political dimension because we want ecological well-being for everyone. What are we denouncing? The predation of forests, of water, of the impact of the natural phenomena that we are experiencing and that are largely our collective responsibility as humans.

¹ An concept in Spanish comparable with hijacking or grabbing.

When I talk about the political dimension, it is integrated with the activism where community feminists have put their bodies. Let's think about the *Zapatistas*, the *Aymara*, the *Mazahua* and many Indigenous peoples who are defending water and land against tree loggers and mining companies. Women who put their bodies to defend territories and vital spaces because they are aware of an intergenerational need.

This leads us to talk about militancy. **How can we be militant, spiritual and activist?** Well, all this goes very well together. What happens is that we have been told that spirituality is a thing of praying and feeling good and that it is not accompanied by militancy and denunciation. But it's not like that. Spirituality is the vital force that drives us to make a complaint, to demand rights, that drives us to raise the cry for justice, and that makes us see that there is a system of predatory corruption. Spirituality awakens all of this in us.

Spirituality is also connected to epistemology. When one is aware of this vital force that inhabits one, the channels of knowledge, investigation, and asking ourselves: why, for what, how, when, who originated it, and in what way, are also open. What is the framework behind the fact that we do not have water, that we do not have land? What is behind a war?

L: Could you tell us about a case in which spiritualities have managed to transform the relationships that exist in a dominant system to a system whose relationship is one of greater well-being and equity?

M: I think of the *Zapatista movement*, which also has a dimension of deep spirituality. They have opted for education, health, solidarity, commerce, and the Earth. These **other forms of interrelation** have attracted many people worldwide to visit the *caracoles*² and learn this other way of governing. And I would like to take this opportunity to denounce that the *Zapatistas* are currently being retreated by organized crime groups

I think of the women of Cherán, the *Mapuche* women in Chile, and some towns in the Amazon. There are many proposals. But precisely, the neocolonial capitalist system that permeates it does not make it visible because it would be its competition, because it is the **other alternative**. I am not saying that these forms of governance are perfect; they also have their flaws, but at least they are alternatives to creating other spaces, providing or looking towards a future for the next generation. Another thing: It seems to me that there is resistance and responsibility on the part of those of us who are already very colonized to decolonize ourselves and enter that other model.

L: We have seen that science connects us with knowledge, and art connects us with emotions and feelings. What does spirituality connect us with?

M: Spirituality connects us with art, dance, music, painting, and poetry because it has a prophetic dimension. By prophetic, I do not mean a person who sees the future but someone who has a deep sensitivity to grasp the benefits of the common good. So, spirituality connects us with ourselves, our interior, and the ethical responsibility of ecojustice. Consequently, it connects us with the relationships we establish with the rest of the human species and other species.

There is a relationship of interconnectivity that is interdependent but not codependent, although many of our trade logic, knowledge and affections are codependent. Here, the proposal of spirituality is to connect us with *interdependence*. Not only with the artistic part, but with the art of eating and eating healthy, with the art of cooking and cooking tasty and nutritious food, with the art of cultivating the land, but, above all, **it connects us with love** because today, in times of war and hatred, **loving each other is subversive**.

² Autonomous municipalities created by the *Zapatistas*, which are independent of local government.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Energy for *yeknemelis*

vision from the Masewal culture, Mexico, that considers the health, harmony, peace and well-being of people on par with the recognition of the intrinsic relationship with the environment, with living beings and the elements of nature that sustain them.

Yek = pure, true, good
Nemelis = life

In the Masewal worldview, the earth, the sun and water are beings whose permission must be asked, since they do not belong to people and, therefore, they must be taken in a responsible, respectful and fraternal way.

The *powkaitalis* principle (taking the other into account) integrates collective thinking and allows participation to avoid the imposition of projects on indigenous and peasant territories.

Energy for **yeknemelis** (the good life) is a project built as a different way of managing energy, improve exchange between generations, defend the gender equality and dialogue between knowledges.

The **yeknemelis** tree is built from reflective processes with the communities that integrate their needs, values and worldviews.

Energy is related to personal well-being and Mother Earth based on mutual care to achieve harmony with the environment and the community, based on community values.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

The healing of the body-territory as cosmogonic and political path

By **Violeta Estefanía Cardona Ruiz**, Postgraduate in Sustainability Sciences, UNAM
Instagram **@sattvayogavi**

What is the body?

The body is a space of complex relationships where both emotions and feelings and bodily relationships converge.

They are inseparable from the social, cultural or historical environment. The historical experience of bodies as cultural constructions is very differentiated (Agua y VIDA, 2017).

Body-territory

This concept emphasizes the parallelism between the body as a place, a territory, that is socially, culturally and historically constructed. Bodies also inhabit a physical space with nature (**territory-Earth**) full of ancestral memories (Cabnal, 2018). The demarcation of human bodies occurs first of all by binary and different sexual bodies: body-woman and body-man. That is why the woman-body is understood as the first territory on which there is oppression.

Resistance and care

In different latitudes of the world, the resistance of women is manifested in defense of their lands, nature and respect for their bodies. They have generated movements, revolts, marches, through collective unity.

Healing

The *Network of Ancestral Healers of Community Feminism, Tz'k'at* in the Quiche Mayan language which means 'network', proposes healing as a cosmic-political path that recovers the emotional, physical and spiritual practices of their ancestors and another way of doing politics and Collective care among women.

The body-territory of indigenous peasant women is crossed by multiple patriarchal violence.

Circles of body-territory defense and healing

Spaces for women to come together, promote the collective defense of the body-territory against patriarchal and colonizing violence. They carry out emotional, physical and spiritual self-care and holistic health practices.

Healing ourselves is a personal and political act [...] we say when you heal, I heal. And by healing I, you heal. It is the reciprocity of healing. We believe that healed bodies are bodies that are also emancipated." (Cabnal en Lissell, 2020)

Spiritual and territorial paths for healing

Defend the body-territory by assuming it as a historical territory in dispute and recovering it as an emancipatory political practice that gives it joy in its relationship with nature.

The **territorial embodiment** involves coming together and acting to collectively defend your body, being and feeling the injustices that bodies and nature experience.

Healing as a cosmic-political path involves revitalizing, energizing and liberating the body to reclaim joy, without losing indignation and resistance, being able to celebrate life through the original cosmogony and plural wisdoms to strengthen the community network through recognition of wisdom in connection with nature.

Territorial alliances and impact on the protection and protection of defenders

References:

Agua y Vida: Mujeres, derechos y ambiente A. C. (2017) Mapeando el cuerpo-territorio.
Cabnal, L. (2015). De las opresiones a las emancipaciones: mujeres indígenas en defensa del territorio cuerpo-tierra. Biodiversidad. Sustento y Culturas.
Cabnal, L. (2018) TZK'AT, Red de Sanadoras Ancestrales de Feminismo Comunitario desde Ixmulew- Guatemala. ecologíaPolítica.
Lissell, Q. (2020) La sanación, un acto feminista emancipatorio (Lorena Cabnal) <https://decolonial.hypotheses.org/2147>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

If you want to continue delving deeper into the topic addressed in this edition, we leave you a list of recommendations that present different perspectives that we hope will provide you with new visions and knowledge.

Serie: *The Good Life*

This series presents the work of nine directors from the indigenous peoples of Colombia who took on the task of telling what good living is for the Arhuaco, Barasano, Wiwa, U'wa, Pastos, Guna Dule, Wayuu, Kamëntšá and Murui. "We are more than indigenous cultures. We are a vision of the world, of the earth and humanity. We can be the solution, are you willing to listen?" Access to the series in the following league:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=N9UVhkVoP6w&list=PLGsF4QfCjgkBuY_5UO11hfTMB-ExO6M

Book: *Politics, emotions and spirituality*

This essay by Natalia Millán invites us to explore the intersection between the political sphere and our lives' personal and transcendental dimensions. Throughout the text, we can discover how our political choices and perceptions of life intertwine, revealing that searching for true autonomy involves a journey towards self-knowledge and personal healing. This book challenges our conventional perspective on politics by interconnecting spiritual and affective elements with the management of power and the common good.

https://www.catarata.org/libro/politica-emociones-y-espiritualidad_149460/

Book: *Laudato Si' Encyclical*

This encyclical, signed by Pope Francis in 2015, focuses on planet Earth as "*the common home*" and the importance of defending nature and its people. It critiques consumerism and irresponsible development and invites global action to combat environmental degradation and mitigate climate change. *Laudato si'* is considered a key text of integral ecology that emphasizes the relationships between the climate and social crises we face as a planet and as humanity.

<https://www.aciprensa.com/Docum/LaudatoSi.pdf>

Magazine: *Sofías*

The magazine *Sofías* (Soffias) is interdisciplinary in nature. In it, you will find philosophical-historical and sociological approaches emphasizing the political dimension of the contexts from which the different reflections emerge to promote critical thinking. It is a space for feminist theological reflection capable of including the "academic" perspective and the multiple diversity of the experiences and wisdom of women who do theology from daily life and their own historical, political, social, religious and cultural contexts.

<http://teologiafeminista.org.mx/sofias/>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Book: *Recovering a Sense of the Sacred: Conversations with Thomas Berry*

This book is a thoughtful and moving memoir by Carolyn W. Toben, chronicling her spiritual journey with renowned scholar, author, and cultural historian Thomas Berry. For ten years, Carolyn spent many hours in deep discussions with Berry about his transformational thinking, which aims to heal the relationship between man and the earth through the recovery of a sense of the sacred. This book is based on his personal notes, practices, and reflections from these conversations.

<https://thomasberry.org/recovering-a-sense-of-the-sacred-conversations-with-thomas-berry/>

Documentary: *The Elephant Whisperers*

This documentary, directed by Kartiki Gonsalves, tells the story of Bomman and Bellie, a rural couple in southern India who raise Ragu and Ammu, two baby elephants, in the Theppakadu camp, which they have been rehabilitating for more than a hundred years. They care for young elephants to prepare them for wildlife, showing that there is an important interspecies relationship to care for, heal and protect each other.

<https://www.netflix.com/title/81312835>

Interview: *VEDAS AND ECOFEMINISM: In conversation with Vandana Shiva*

In this interview, Rajiv Malhotra of Infinity Foundation speaks with Dr. Vandana Shiva, who explains her pioneering role in bringing Vedic ideas embedded in ecofeminism to the West. Vandana Shiva is a scientist, philosopher and ecofeminist activist known worldwide for her work linked to the global environmental movement, for which she received a Nobel Prize in honor of her alternative and peaceful revolutionary struggle.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mGC1DxyISNY>

Book: *Sacred nature*

In this work, Karen Armstrong, British writer and historian of religions, explores how many people revered nature and made it sacred, contrasting with a modern vision that has tended to exploit it. Through a combination of history, religion, and philosophy, the author analyzes how this disconnection has contributed to the current environmental crisis, as well as actions that can revitalize each one has connection with nature. A fragment can be found in the following link:

https://proassetspdlcom.cdnstatics2.com/usuaris/libros_contenido/arxius/51/50947_Naturaleza_sagrada.pdf

Mexico City, Mexico, 2024